

“A Study To Assess The Knowledge Of Mothers Regarding The Impact Of Smart Phone Usage On Psychosocial Well Being Of Under Five Children At Selected Community, Thrissur”

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ABSTRACT: Mobile phone are considered as an important communication tool and have become integral part of the society, it is not only a communication device but it is also a necessary social accessory. Nowadays children under five are too dependent on smart phones. The present study focuses on assessing the knowledge of mothers regarding the impact of smart phone usage on psychosocial wellbeing of under five children at selected community, Thrissur. The objectives of the study was to assess the knowledge of mothers regarding the impact of smart phone usage of psychosocial wellbeing of under five children and to associate the level of knowledge of mothers regarding the impact of smart phone usage on psychosocial wellbeing of under five children with their selected demographic variables. A descriptive sample design was adapted for the study. The study was conducted among 60 mothers, who were selected by convenience sampling techniques. The mothers knowledge was assessed by using a structured knowledge questionnaire regarding the impact of smart phones usages on psychosocial well being. The findings revealed that 34(56.67%) of mothers had good knowledge. 24(40%) had moderate knowledge and 2(3.33%) had poor knowledge regarding impact of smart phone usage on psychosocial wellbeing. The analysis showed that there is a significant association between the gender of child, age of child and information regarding the impact of excessive smart phone usage.

Keywords: *Mobile phone, addiction, psychosocial wellbeing*

INTRODUCTION

The worldwide technology and its changes play a major role in each individual's life. The current trend of the society is to adopt every change in the field of communication technology. The mobile phones are boon to this century. Mobile phone are considered as an important communication tool and have become an integral part of the society; it is not only a communication device but it also a necessary social accessory. Nowadays children are too dependent on smart phones. Smartphone addiction has become extremely common not just among adults but even kids. About 23.80% of children are said to use smartphones while they are in bed, before going to

sleep and 37.15% of children, always or frequently, experience reduced levels of concentration due to smartphone usage, as per a study conducted by National Commission for Protection of Child Rights. Excessive screen media usage in children can have both positive and negative impacts on their development. Regarding cognitive development, screens have the potential to enhance education and learning. However, studies have shown that excessive screen time and media multitasking can negatively affect executive functioning, sensor motor development, and academic outcomes. Early screen exposure has been associated with lower cognitive abilities and academic performance in later years.

Language development is also affected by screen time, as

NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Smart phone addiction can always refer to the compulsive and excessive reliance or need of mobile phone in a child's life. Hence this study implies its importance in this current scenario. A smart phone is an easy gate way to access social media. It helps to engage each and every one despite being child, adult or old to involve in its world. So when a child gets hold of phone he or she lose control over its usage. This may result neglecting their responsibilities, relationship and exhibit restlessness and anxiety when he or she is unable to access the phone. According to statistics in 2022 about 83.72% of world population over 6 billion people use smart phone with young people being most common users. According to global statistics 804 million children under 14 age have mobile phone in that 20% children under the age of 5 own smart phone. While knowing the factors in India 33.3% are addicted to mobile phone. This indicate the usage of smart phone around the world which is increasing steadily and its increasing in an alarming rate. Mobile phone affect children in many ways. First and for most Text neck which cause pressure and strain on your neck. Also poor sleep hygiene, tendinitis which basically effect your fingers, distracted travelling, decreased concentration and learning issues, less physical activity, eyesight problems, lack of personal communication and also peer pressure. Along with this psychologically this can lead a child to depression, anxiety and sometimes leads to social withdrawal. Smart phone have a positive attribute and benefits but that does not nullifies the negative it have on one's life physically and psychologically.

Statement of the study

A study to assess the knowledge of mothers regarding the impact of smart phone usage on the psycho social well being of under five children in a selected Community Thrissur.

Objectives of the study

- 1) To assess the knowledge of mothers regarding the impact of smart phone usage on the psycho social wellbeing of under five children.
- 2) To associate the level of knowledge of mothers regarding the impact of smart phone usage on psycho social wellbeing of under five children with selected demographic variables.

Hypothesis

H₁ : There is a significant association between knowledge of mothers regarding impact of smart phone usage on psycho social well being of under five children with selected demographic variables.

H₀ : There is no significant association between knowledge of mothers regarding impact of smart phone usage on psycho social well being of under five children with selected demographic variables.

METHODOLOGY

Research Approach: This study adopted quantitative approach. Data collection procedure consists of gathering information to address the research problem. A formal permission to conduct the study was obtained from

Methods of data collection

Data collection procedure are the means of gathering information to address the research problem. A formal permission was obtained principal, Aswini College of Nursing followed by the

investigators got permission from the Pananchery Panchayat, Thrissur. Data collection period was from 16/08/2023 to 18/08/2023. The researcher assured that the study will not interfere with the daily routines of mothers. The investigator established a good rapport with the mothers and explained the purpose of the study and requested their full cooperation. Then the investigator collected data from 60 samples who were selected through convenient sampling technique. They were explained about the purpose and anonymity of the study. Prepared demographic profile and knowledge questionnaire along with instructions were given to them. The time taken for completing the questionnaire was 20mins. Answers were recorded after their response. All samples were cooperative during data collection.

Research design: A non experimental descriptive research design was used in this study.

Demographic variable: In this study the demographic variable are age, gender, annual income, type of family, educational qualification, occupational status, information for mothers regarding impact of mobile phone use, number of mobile phone in house, time of mobile phone used by child.

Accessible population: Accessible population is the aggregate of cases that confirm the designated criteria and that are accessible. In this study the accessible population is the mothers of under five children at Panachery Grama Panchayat , Thrissur.

Sampling technique: The samples were collected non probability convenient sampling technique .

Sample size: The sample size for t study is 60 mothers of under five children residing at ward 20 and 23 of Pananchery Panchayath Thrissur.

Criteria for sample collection

Following criteria were adopted for selection at the sample for this study.

Inclusion criteria:

- Mothers who are residing in Pananchery Grama Panchayath
- Mothers who are willing to participate in this study
- Mothers who are able to read and write Malayalam
- Mothers of under five children who are available during data collection

Exclusion criteria:

- Mothers of under five children who were not present in the house on the day of data collection.

Description and scoring

Section A: Description of demographic profile of mothers

Section B: Description of level of knowledge of mothers about excessive mobile phone usage.

Section C: Description of association between levels of knowledge of subjects with their selected demographic variable.

RESULT FINDINGS:

Section A: Description of demographic profile of mothers

Table: 1. Frequency and percentage distribution of mothers according to the age in years.

SL. NO	DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1.	Age of mother		
	a) <20 year	4	6.7%
	b) 20 – 30 year	37	61.7%
	c) 30 – 40 year	19	31.6%
	d) 40 year and above	0	0
2.	Age of child		
	a) 0-2 years	19	31.7
	b) 2-3 years	13	21.6
	c) 3-4 years	12	20
	d) 4-5 years	16	26.7
3.	Educational qualification mother		
	a) Primary education 3 5	3	5
	b) Higher secondary education	20	33.3
	c) Graduation	31	51.7
	d) Post graduation	6	10
4.	Gender of child		
	a) Male	32	53.3
	b) Female	28	46.7
5.	Monthly income		
	a) < 50000	3	5
	b) 5000 – 10000	16	26.7
	c) 10000 – 20000	26	43.33
	d) > 20,000	15	25
6.	Type of family		
	a) nuclear family	34	56.7
	b) joint family	25	41.66
	c) extended family	1	1.67
7.	Occupation of mother		
	a) professional	10	16.7
	b) skilled	7	11.6
	c) self employed	5	8.33
	d) unemployed	38	63.33
8.	Information on hazards mobile phone over usage		
	a) no information	4	6.7
	b) mass media	41	68.3
		12	20

	c) health workers d) others	3	5
9.	No. of mobile phones in home a) 1 b) 2 c) 3 d) 3 and more	3 18 23 16	5 30 38.33 26.67
10.	time spend in mobile phone by the child a) less than or equal to 1 hour b) 30 minutes to 1 hour c) 1-2 hour d) more than 2 hours	40 12 4 4	66.67 20 6.67 6.67

SECTION B

Description of the assessment of level of the knowledge of mothers regarding the impact of excessive usage of mobile phone in psychosocial wellbeing.

LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE	RANGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Inadequate	1-10	2	34
Moderate	11-20	24	40%
Adequate	21-30	34	56.67%

SECTION C

Description of the association between the level of knowledge of the subject with their selected demographic variables.

SL. NO	DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLE	χ^2	Table value(TB)
1.	Age of child	15.57*	12.59
2.	Gender of child	15.31*	12.59
3.	Information regarding impact of excessive smart phone usage	13.9*	12.59

DISCUSSION

The first objective was to assess the knowledge of mothers regarding the impact of smart phone usage on psycho social wellbeing of under five children:

The present study findings revealed that among 60 mothers 34(56.67%) having good knowledge, 24(40%) having moderate knowledge and 2(3.33%) having poor knowledge.

The second objective was to associate the level of knowledge of mothers regarding the impact of smart phone usage on psycho social wellbeing of under five children with their selected demographic variables.

CONCLUSION

The aim of the study was to assess the knowledge of mothers regarding the impact of smart phone usage on psycho social wellbeing of under five children. The study reached in a conclusion that the mothers are having adequate knowledge about the psycho social impact of mobile phones.

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